

ASTRONOMY

VERY "FRESH" IMPACT CRATERS INDICATE FROZEN WATER IN THE SURFACE LAYER OF THE SOIL

Vidmachenko A.

*Doctor Phys.-Math. Sci., Professor, Professor of Department of Physics
National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

Now the entire surface of Mars is bound by permafrost. Its thickness reaches one kilometer at the equator and increases to six kilometers at the poles. However, ravines formed by water flows and mud flows inside some craters indicate the release of liquid from the melted layer of permafrost. Changes in the appearance of some ravines can be formed both by liquid and by the shedding of dry soil on a steep slope. There are many more arguments in favor of water. A comparison of images of the Martian surface obtained with the help of the "Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter's" equipment after only a few years, and even months, made it possible to discover a significant number of newly formed impact craters. For example, the obtained direct images of the surface of Mars with high spatial resolution allowed to register the presence of "fresh" impact craters with the diameter of the funnels from 2 to 148 m and the depth from 0.4 to several meters. The age of these impact craters at the time of beginning of observations was from several months to 4 years. Observations of the material ejected from these craters using the "CRISM" panoramic spectrometer, operating in the visible and near-infrared regions of the spectrum, made it possible to obtain spectral evidence of the presence of water ice in particular. The light spots around all the craters decreased in size over time. The rate of evaporation of this substance proved that it is very pure ice, which consists of at least 99% water. Images of craters taken with the "HIRISE" camera have provided the first evidence of ice on the surface of Mars halfway between the North Pole and the equator. The distribution of the ejected material around all these craters showed that the upper limit of the ice layer in the places where the meteorites fell is at a depth of more than 0.1 m. The obtained images of these "fresh" impact craters directly proved the presence of pure water ice on the surface of Mars in the mid-latitudes of the planet, and then near the equator.

Keywords: Mars, permafrost, impact craters, soil erosion, water ice.

Calculations and observational data show that now all of Mars is bound by permafrost [39]. Its thickness reaches one kilometer at the equator and increases to six kilometers at the poles [10]. However, distinct ravines formed by gullies from liquid flows and mud flows inside some large craters [28, 29, 34, 38] indicate periodic outflow of liquid from the melted layer of permafrost. Changes in the appearance of some ravines, events over several years of observation, first noted in 2005, are still a matter of controversy: they were formed by liquid water, or they are traces of dry soil falling down a steep slope. There are many more arguments in favor of water [8, 13, 21]. In general, this planet remains a frozen permafrost, in which all the water that once filled the now dry riverbeds and depressions of many craters is hidden. In 2008, the automatic station "Phoenix" (Fig. 1, left) in the area near the northern polar cap of Mars revealed with its mini excavator a layer of water ice at a depth of several centimeters from the surface.

Comparison of those presented in Fig. 1 (right) of two images taken on the 20th and 24th Martian days of the Phoenix rover's stay on the subpolar part of the Martian surface allows us to follow the effects of the evaporation of frozen soil particles. The close-up images show a depression dug by the lander in the Martian soil [20, 37]. These days seasonally [6, 14-18, 22, 25, 35] correspond to June 15 and 18 according to the Earth calendar. Small light pieces in the lower left part of the indentation are clearly visible in the photo on the left, taken on day 20; by the 24th day – they have already completely disappeared. This is a clear indication that these pieces were water ice that had melted. Here we see an example of so-called sublimation, in which solid ice directly turns into steam, bypassing the liquid state. The ice that "Phoenix" found lay at a depth of 7-8 cm under a layer of brown soil, not far from the edge of the polar cap, which has shrunk with the arrival of the polar summer.

Fig. 1. Left – the engines of the Phoenix lander blew away the upper layer of dust and exposed the frozen water ice. On the right – ice under the "shovel" of the "Phoenix" module (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

Some calculations show that ice should also be present at latitudes of about 60° ; but it should lie there deeper than 20-30 cm from the surface. To test this theory, it is enough to dig into the Martian soil a little more than this depth. The last to dig trenches in the middle latitudes was the "Viking-2" apparatus. But at the end of the 1970s, he dug into the Martian soil to a depth of 15 cm, without getting to the ice by some 5-15 cm. That is why he did not see any solid ice there. According to the authors of the paper [1], Mars could have been one and a half times wetter just a few thousand years ago. There are several theories as to how exactly a layer of such pure ice formed beneath the surface of Mars. It was proposed that the ice on Mars formed in the same way that pure ice crystals form under the surface of the Earth – when the soil "freezes". Nature itself helped to solve this issue. Since the atmosphere of Mars [3, 19, 23] is very thin, it practically does not protect the planet

from impacts on its surface by meteorites and asteroids. And that is why they reach its surface much more often and form fresh craters some meters deep on Mars [1, 5, 39].

When conducting a search for fresh craters, images of the Martian surface obtained using the equipment of the "Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter" ("MRO") were used. The discovery of such "white-blue" craters began in August 2008, when images from the orbiter were examined for any dark spots or other changes that were not visible on previously obtained images of the same area. A few days later, spectral evidence of the presence of ice was obtained from the "MRO" orbiter using the "CRISM" ("Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars") panoramic spectrometer, which operates in the visible and near-infrared regions of the spectrum. Two of these craters were only 70 m apart and formed almost simultaneously (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Dynamics of changes in the visibility of the ice knocked out by meteorites on the surface of Mars (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

Light spots around all craters decreased in size over time. In order to make sure that it is water, infrared spectra of reflected light from these areas of the surface were obtained. The spectra clearly indicated the presence of water precisely in the blue points shown in Fig. 2. The rate of evaporation of this substance also proved that it is very pure ice, which consists of at least 99% water. The obtained direct images of the surface of Mars with high spatial resolution also confirmed the presence of very clean and bright ice in craters (Fig. 3) with diameters of pits from 4 to 12 m and depths from 0.4 to 2.5 m at five different sites on Mars. The age of

these impact craters at the time of beginning of observations was from several months to 4 years. The distribution of the ejected soil and light spots inside and around the craters shows that the upper limit of the ice layer in the places where the meteoroids fell lies at a depth of 10 to 35 cm, and the thickness of its occurrence was from several centimeters to meters and possibly more. Thus, images of craters obtained with the "HIRISE" camera provided the first evidence of ice on the surface of Mars halfway between the North Pole and the equator.

Fig. 3. Images of the crater obtained on 18.10.2008 (left) and 14.01.2009 (right) using the HIRISE camera from the apparatus «Mars Reconnaissance Orbiter» (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

A comparative analysis of images of almost 98% of the Martian surface, obtained in 1999, and again in 2006 – on 30% of the planet's surface, revealed two dozen new craters with diameters from 2 to 148 m. They are very important for determining the age of various geological formations on the surface of Mars. Strong winds and dust storms cause the erosion of details on the surface and the appearance of eolian deposits and dunes [7, 9]. For example, the analysis of the images of the southern subpolar region obtained by the "Mariner-9" spacecraft for 4 months, according to the nature of erosion, allowed to distinguish three main geological structures there: the most ancient cratered area

covered with pot-shaped depressions, a plateau about a billion years old and the youngest areas of a layered structure several million years old, or even less. The age of the first two types of terrain is sufficient even to support some life forms there [4, 11, 12, 24, 26, 27, 30, 31]. Later, it turned out that the erosion of the craters of this area is practically indistinguishable from the background of the entire surface [20, 29, 30]. Many completely "fresh" impact craters have now been found, which are formed after the fall of meteorite bodies [33]. Light spots around them decreased in size over time (Fig. 4). And their infrared spectra clearly indicated the presence of frozen water there.

Fig. 4. On the left – an image of a crater with a diameter of about 12 m, formed between 07.03.2004 and 06.28.2008 at middle latitudes. On the right – another "fresh" crater found in September 2009, almost on the equator, with a diameter of about 8 m (<http://photojournal.jpl.nasa.gov/>).

For example, on the photos of the surroundings of the Arcadia and Utopia plains obtained with the help of the "HIRISE" camera – in the Northern Hemisphere of Mars, it was possible to register more than 9 dozen "fresh" craters with sizes from 1 to 15 meters and a depth of up to 2.5 meters, in just one year. Emissions

from them confirmed the presence of clean and bright water ice (Fig. 4). After only a few months, this ice evaporated. The distribution of the ejected material around all these craters showed that the upper limit of the ice layer in the places where the meteorite bodies fell is at a depth of more than 10 cm. It was previously

believed that the ice accumulated below the surface between soil particles. That is, it was suggested to be a 50:50 mixture of mud and ice. But careful studies of direct images and analysis of the corresponding spectral data allowed us to find out that the white material ejected from the impact craters actually consists of only 1% mud and 99% water ice. Such purity of ice is still unclear. And according to calculations, in order to explain the appearance of ice at the latitudes where it is observed, the humidity of the Martian atmosphere at the time of the formation of the ice layer should be one and a half times higher than it is now. At the same time, we are not talking about the distant "wet past" that existed on Mars billions of years ago.

That is, the obtained images of these "fresh" impact craters directly proved the presence of pure water ice on the surface of Mars, first at half the distance [2] between the North Pole and the equator, and then even at the equator.

References

1. Byrne S., Dundas C.M., Kennedy M.R., et al. (2009) Distribution of mid-latitude ground ice on Mars from new impact craters. *Science*. 325, p. 1674-1676.
2. Dundas C.M., Bramson A.M., Ojha L., et al. (2018) Exposed subsurface ice sheets in the Martian mid-latitudes. *Science*. 359(6372), p. 199-201.
3. Kahn R. (1985) The evolution of CO₂ on Mars. *Icarus*. 62(2), p. 175-190.
4. Kuznyetsova Yu.G., Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2019) What can be called "traces" of life on Mars. 6-th Gamow ICo in Odessa and 19-th Gamow Summer School, Ukraine, Odessa, August 11-18, 2019, p. 52-53.
5. Malin M.C., 195 Edgett K.S., Posiolova L.V., et al. (2006) Present-Day Impact Cratering Rate and Contemporary Gully Activity on Mars. *Science*, 314(5805), p. 1573-1577.
6. Morozhenko A.V., Vidmachenko A.P. (2005) Polarimetry and Physics of Solar System Bodies. *Photopolarimetry in Remote Sensing, NATO Science Series II: Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry*. 161, p 369-384.
7. Morozhenko A.V., Vidmachenko A.P. (2017) Optical parameters of Martian dust and its influence on the exploration of Mars. *Dust in the Atmosphere of Mars and Its Impact on Human Exploration, Proceedings conf. 13-15 June, Houston, Texas. LPI Contribution No. 1966, 2017, id. 6010.*
8. Morozhenko A.V., Vidmachenko A.P. (2017) What and how can affect the exploration of Mars. 19 International scientific conference *Astronomical School of Young Scientists*. May 24-25, 2017. Bila Tserkva, Ukraine, 67-69.
9. Morozhenko A.V., Vidmachenko A.P. (2020) Dust can affect on the mastering of Mars. 22 International scientific conference *Astronomical School of Young Scientists*. December 11-12, 2020. Kyiv, Ukraine, p. 71-73.
10. Plaut J.J., Picardi G., Safaeinili A., et al. (2007). *Subsurface Radar Sounding of the South Polar Layered Deposits of Mars*. *Science*. 316 (5821), p. 92-95.
11. Steklov A.F. Vidmachenko A.P. (2019) Where and What Exactly Can Be the "Traces" of Life on Mars? The Mars Extant Life: What's Next? conference, November 5-8, 2019. National C. and K. Res. Institute, New Mexico. #5089. LPI Co. No. 2108.
12. Steklov A.F., Vidmachenko A.P. (2019) In what places and what exactly can be the "traces" of life on Mars? 9 ICo on Mars, Pasadena, California, July 22-25, 2019, LPI Co. No. 2089, 6007.
13. Vidmachenko A.P., Morozhenko A.V. (2005) Mapping of the physical characteristics and mineral composition of a superficial layer of the Moon or Mars and ultra-violet polarimetry from the orbital station. 36th Annual Lunar and Planetary Science Conference, March 14-18, 2005, in League City, Texas #1015.
14. Vidmachenko A.P. (2000) Variations of the Reflective Characteristics of Jupiter's Atmosphere. 31st Annual Lunar and Planetary Science Conference, March 13-17, 2000. 1060
15. Vidmachenko A.P. (1997) Temporal changes in methane absorption in Jupiter's atmosphere. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies*. 13(6), p. 21-25.
16. Vidmachenko A.P. (1985) Activity of processes in the atmosphere of Jupiter. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies* 1(5), p. 101-102.
17. Vidmachenko A.P. (1987) Manifestation of seasonal variations in the atmosphere of Saturn. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies*. 3(6), p. 9-12.
18. Vidmachenko A.P. (1994) Variations in the brightness of celestial objects in astronomical observations mount Maidanak. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies* 10 (5), 52-56.
19. Vidmachenko A.P. (2009) Planetary atmospheres. *Astronomical School's Report*. 6(1), p. 56-68.
20. Vidmachenko A.P. (2009) Research of the Mars by space vehicles. *Astronomical School's Report*. 6(1-2), p. 131-137.
21. Vidmachenko A.P. (2009) Water on Mars. *Astron. almanac*. 56, p. 225-249.
22. Vidmachenko A.P. (2015) Seasons on Saturn. II. Influence of solar activity on variation of methane absorption. *Astronomical School's Report* 11 (1), 15-23.
23. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Activity of processes on the visible surfaces of Solar System bodies. *Astronomical School's Report* 12 (1), p. 14-26.
24. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Is there life on Mars and where necessary to search for its traces. *Astronomy and present: materials of 5 Interregional Scientific Conference*. April 12, 2016. Vinnytsia, Ukraine. P. 43-48.
25. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Seasonal changes on Jupiter: 1. Factor of activity of the hemispheres. *Kinematics and Physics of Celestial Bodies* 32 (4), 189-195.
26. Vidmachenko A.P. (2016) Traces of life on Mars must be sought around the valley Hellas in areas where the water coming out from under the planet's sur-

face. 18 International scientific conference Astronomical School of Young Scientists. Kyiv, Ukraine. May 26-27, 2016, p. 14-16.

27. Vidmachenko A.P. (2017) Where Should Search Traces of Life, Which Could Appear on Mars in the First 300 Million Years. Fourth ICo on Early Mars: Geologic, Hydrologic, and Climatic Evolution and the Implications for Life. 2014. 3005.

28. Vidmachenko A.P. (2018) Comparative features of volcanoes on Solar system bodies. 20 International scientific conference Astronomical School of Young Scientists, May 23-24. Uman, Ukraine, p. 9-12.

29. Vidmachenko A.P. (2018) Modern volcanic activity on the Moon. 20 International scientific conference Astronomical School of Young Scientists. May 23-24, 2018. Uman, Ukraine, p. 5-7.

30. Vidmachenko A.P. (2019) Traces of life on Mars should be sought in emissions from the crater Hellas in places where water exits from under the surface. New Trends in Astrophysics, Cosmology and HEP after Gamow, p. 45.

31. Vidmachenko A.P. (2019) Traces of Martian Life Should be Sought in Places Around Hellas Crater, Where Water has Recently Spilled Out onto the Surface. Ninth International Conference on Mars, Pasadena, California, Jul 22-25, 2019, LPI Contrib. No. 2089, 6005.

32. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) Comparison of features of impact and volcanic craters on the surface of Mars. Proceed. of VIII Intern. Sc. and Pract. Conf. Progr. Res. m. w. (27-29.04.2023). Ch. 43. BoScience Publisher, Boston, USA, p. 237-246.

33. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) History of possible climate change on Mars. Proceedings of VII International Scientific and Practical Conference. Science and

innovation of modern world. (23-25 March 2023). Chapter 54. Cognum Publishing House, London, United Kingdom, p. 336-345.

34. Vidmachenko A.P. (2023) Macrorelief of the surface of Mars. Proceedings of XIV ISPCo. Prospects for the development of science and the environment. (April 10-12, 2023). Chapter 7. Helsinki, Finland, p. 34-39.

35. Vidmachenko A.P., Klimenko V.M., Morozhenko A.V. (1981) Apparent spectral albedos of the disk of Mars in September-October 1977. Solar System Research. 14(4), p. 157-159.

36. Vidmachenko A.P., Mozghovyi O.V., Steklov O.F. (2023) Very "fresh" craters on the surface of Mars. Proceedings of 11 All-Ukrainian Scientific Conference "Astronomy and present day", April 12, 2023. Vinnytsia, Ukraine. LLC "TVORY", p. 71-76.

37. Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2020) Mineral resources can be mined on different bodies of the Solar System. 22 International Astronomical School of Young Scientists. December 11-12, 2020. Kyiv, Ukraine, p. 89-92.

38. Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2022) Features of volcanic structures on Venus. Proceedings of the 9th International scientific and practical conference. Modern directions of scientific research development. 29, p. 195-204.

39. Vidmachenko A.P., Steklov A.F. (2022) How long ago has water flowed on Mars surface? Results of modern scientific research and development. Proceedings of XI ISPCo. Barca Academy Publishing, Madrid, Spain. 16-18.01.2022. P. 226-232.